

**DRUG REVIEW ON SIDDHA FORMULATION ANDA LEGHIUM FOR PITHA
GUNMAM (DUODENAL ULCER)**

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ABSTRACT

The siddha system of medicine is one of the earliest traditional medical system in the world and deals with physical, psychological, social and spiritual well being of an individual. Siddha system has several indigenous preparations which is obtained from herbals, minerals and animal products. Among these I have selected the topic duodenal ulcer as siddha term pitha gunmam. Duodenal ulcer is the most common type of peptic ulceration and is four times more prevalent than gastric ulcer. This review describes the phytochemical and pharmacological action of each ingredient used in this formulations.

KEYWORDS: Siddha system, Anda leghium, Pitha gunmam, Phytochemistry, Pharmacological actions.

INTRODUCTION

The siddha system of medicine is one of the earliest traditional medical system in the world and deals with physical, psychological, social and spiritual well being of an individual. The panchekaranam theory of siddha science explains the origin and formation of the basic elements of five primordial elements viz. earth, water, fire, air and space and so is man. These elements always act in mutual coordination and can never act independently. Siddha system is guiding us to lead a perfect living in this world, starting from the first day of birth to the death. Duodenal ulcer is the most common

type of peptic ulceration and is four times more prevalent than gastric ulcer. This drug review select only one as easily available raw materials and easy to preparation of medicine and wide range of indication were found in "Anda leghium". It was has 07 ingredients among all only one animal product. Hen egg white and other all from plant origin. Which is mentioned in siddha literature of Noigaluku siddha parigaram. This drug use for pitha gunmam. This review article describes the phytochemical and pharmacological action of the part of each ingredient used in this formulation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

INGREDIENTS OF ANDA LEGIUM

S.NO	INGREDIENTS	BOTANICAL NAME	FAMILY	PARTS USED	DOSE
1	Elumichai palam	Citrus limon	Rutaceae	Fruit	25
2	Kozhi muttai	Gallus gallus domesticus	Phasianidae	Egg albumen	25
3	Seeragam	Cuminum cyminum	Apiaceae	Seed	35gms
4	Sombu	Pimpinella anisum	Apiaceae	Seed	35gms
5	Sarkkarai	Saccharum officinarum	Poaceae	-	875gms
6	Cow's ghee	-	-	-	175gms
7	Honey	-	-	-	175gms

METHOD OF PREPARATION

Separate the egg white and put it in a bowl. Squeeze in some lemon juice and dissolve sugar in it. Place it on the stove over a low flame and heat it until it reaches a syrup like consistency. Sprinkle cumin and fennel powder into

the mixture and stir well. Add ghee and remove from heat. Once it cools down, add honey and mix well.

DOSAGE: Kalarchikai azhavu, Twice a day, Before food.

DURATION: 30 days.

S.NO	INGREDIENTS	PHYTOCHEMICALS/CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS	PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITY
1	Elumichai palam	Flavonoids, Phenolic acids, Saponins, Sterols	Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, Anti-bacterial
2	Kozhimuttai	Bio active compounds: Proteins & peptides, Lysozyme, Ovalbumin	Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, Anti-bacterial
3	Seeragam	Cuminaldehyde, P-cymene, Flavonoids, Tannins, Saponins	Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, Digestive stimulant
4	Sombu	Essential oil, Anisaldehyde, Cisanetholes	Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, Alalgescic
5	Sarkkarai	Fatty acids, Flavonoids, Phenolic acids	Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, Analgesic
6	Cow's ghee	Palmitic, stearic and myristic acids, Mono unsaturated fatty acids	Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant
7	Honey	Flavonoids, Phenolic acids, Coumarins, Terpenes	Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Siddha system of medicines are being practiced by a large population in south india. The development of this traditional system of medicine with perspective of safety, efficacy and quality will help not only & preserve the traditional heritage but also to rationalize the use of natural products in health care. Plants serve as vast source for varied phytoconstituents exhibiting pharmacological property. The ingredients of Anda leghium having antioxidant, anti inflammatory, antibacterial, analgesic, immunomodulatory. Activity our finding demonstrates that Anda leghium drastically reduce upper abdominal pain, heartburn, indigestion, nausea, vomiting & loss of appetite. The citrus limon is extensively studied for its pharmacological activities of antioxidant, anti inflammatory, antibacterial activity, then juice of the fruit is used to treat reduces gastric secretion & it protect the gastric lining from damage. Gallus gallus domesticus having antibacterial, antioxidant and anti inflammatory property. Which helps to healing and repairing duodenal lining damage. Cuminum cyminum, Pimpinella anisum and Saccharum officinarum having antioxidant, anti inflammatory, analgesic property. Which helps to maintain the PH of the gastric environment, inhibiting stomach acid and reduce the severity of ulcer induced agents. Cow's ghee possess antioxidant & anti inflammatory activity which helps to heal the ulcer inside the intestinal tract & reduces acidity. Honey possess antioxidant and anti inflammatory activity which treating peptic ulcers & PH regulation. Our findings suggest that, siddha preparations have great potential as antioxidant and anti inflammatory agent against many enteric pathogens. Thus, these preparations can be used to control or prevent the peptic ulcer disease. It is useful in the treatment of pitha gunmam (Duodenal ulcer).

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